

And the Oscar goes to: Death-feigning behavior in *Stenocercus squarrosus* Nogueira & Rodrigues, 2006 (Squamata, Tropicuridae)

Maria Regilane Belo da Silva¹, João Antonio de Araujo Filho², Igor Joventino Roberto³, Samuel Cardozo Ribeiro^{1*}

1. Universidade Federal do Cariri - UFCA, Instituto de Formação de Educadores-IFE, Laboratório de Biologia e Ecologia de Animais Silvestres – LABE-AS, 63260000, Brejo Santo, CE, Brazil.

2. Universidade Regional do Cariri - URCA, Centro de Ciências Biológicas e da Saúde – CCBS, 63150000, Campos Sales, CE, Brazil.

3. Universidade Estadual do Ceará, Faculdade de Filosofia Dom Aureliano Matos, 62.930-000, Limoeiro do Norte, CE, Brazil.

* Corresponding author. E-mail: samuel.ribeiro@ufca.edu.br

Editor: Henrique Caldeira Costa

Submetido: 26-02-2025

Aceito: 29-07-2025

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17376927](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17376927)

Resumo

Este estudo apresenta o primeiro registro do comportamento defensivo de tanatose (fingimento de morte) em *Stenocercus squarrosus*, observado durante um inventário herpetofaunístico realizado no município de Caldeirão Grande do Piauí, estado do Piauí, Brasil. Ao perceber a aproximação do observador ou após um leve toque, o indivíduo correu rapidamente cerca de 10–15 cm e, em seguida, lançou-se ao solo, achatando o corpo dorsoventralmente contra o substrato e estendendo os membros alternadamente em cada lado do corpo. Tal comportamento defensivo, observado sem manuseio direto do lagarto, é especialmente raro. Este registro fornece novas informações comportamentais que ampliam o conhecimento sobre a história natural de *S. squarrosus*, uma espécie considerada elusiva e rara.

Palavras Chave: Caatinga, Comportamento defensivo, Lagartos, Tanatose

Abstract

This study provides the first record of thanatosis (death-feigning behavior) in *Stenocercus squarrosus*, observed during a herpetofaunal inventory in the municipality of Caldeirão Grande do Piauí, state of Piauí, Brazil. Upon detecting the observer's approach or following a slight touch, the individual rapidly fled approximately 10–15 cm before abruptly dropping to the ground, pressing its body dorsoventrally against the substrate, and extending its limbs alternately along each side of the body. Such a defensive display occurring without direct handling is particularly rare among lizards. This observation contributes novel behavioral information to the natural history of *S. squarrosus*, a species regarded as both elusive and rare.

Key-words: Caatinga, Defensive Behavior, Lizards, Thanatosis

Defensive behavior in animals is characterized by a set of elements and strategies used to avoid or reduce situations of threats or risk of predation (Bauder et al., 2015; Santos et al., 2010). These behaviors have been shaped throughout the evolutionary process, some being simpler and others quite complex. In lizards there is a wide variety of defensive behaviors involving active and passive strategies (Miranda et al., 2022; Montoya-Cruz & Díaz-Flórez, 2023). Flight is the most common active strategy, used when the lizard seeks to escape quickly; other behaviors include biting the aggressor or using the tail in defense, and many resort to caudal autotomy to distract and escape predators (Montoya-Cruz & Díaz-Flórez, 2023). Among passive strategies, cryptic coloration, which allows camouflage with the surroundings, and death feigning, tonic immobility, or thanatosis, in which the lizard simulates death to discourage potential attacks (Miyatake, 2001). These adaptive behaviors vary among species, demonstrating the diversity of defense mechanisms within the group (Rocha, 1993; Rocha & Van Sluys, 2008). This diversity results from the evolutionary and adaptive process between predator and prey to survive predation attempts (Rocha, 1993; Santos et al., 2010; Sannolo et al., 2014).

Thanatosis may be the last effective defensive resort in situations of extreme threat, mainly when the individual is captured. Stress is likely one of the factors determining this process, forcing the animal to assume an immobility posture, appearing dead (with rigid muscles and, in some cases, closed eyelids) (Bertoluci et al., 2006; Humphreys & Ruxton, 2018; Miranda et al., 2022; Montoya-Cruz & Díaz-Flórez, 2023). Thanatosis has been investigated repeatedly due to its occurrence in various animal groups (Arduino & Gould, 1984). Death simulation apparently aims to confuse predators that do not usually ingest dead prey (Travaglia-Cardoso, 2014), avoiding direct confrontations and thus reducing risk for the prey. Therefore, this behavior is especially effective against predators that rely on visual capture of prey and also in situations where chances of escape are minimal (Machado-Filho et al., 2018).

According to records cited in the literature, thanatosis is observed in arthropods (Oliver, 1996; Miyatake, 2001), fish (Resende et al., 2025), anurans (Sazima, 1974; Vrcibradic & Van Sluys, 2000), and snakes (Jelić & Vilaj, 2011; Fuentes et al., 2021). Among lizards, this behavior was

recorded in several families: Crotaphytidae (e.g. Gluesing, 1983), Liolaemidae (e.g. Rocha, 1993), Scincidae (e.g. Langkilde et al., 2003), Dibamidae (e.g. Torres-Cervantes et al., 2004), Gymnophthalmidae (e.g. Mesquita et al., 2018; Alves & Cavalcanti, 2024), and Tropicuridae (e.g. Galdino & Pereira, 2002).

Tropicurid lizards of the genus *Stenocercus* Duméril & Bibron, 1837 are found in South America, inhabiting both lowlands and high altitudes. *Stenocercus* is the most diverse genus within Tropicuridae, including 80 species (Uetz et al., 2025) distributed across several vegetation domains (Torres-Carvajal, 2000). *Stenocercus squarrosus* Nogueira and Rodrigues, 2006; after the name of the species (Fig.1A) is a terrestrial, diurnal species with a relictual distribution in Caatinga and Caatinga-Cerrado transition areas (Carrasco) in the states of Ceará and Piauí at elevations ranging from 259 to 919 meters (Nogueira & Rodrigues, 2006; Ribeiro et al., 2009; Cavalcanti et al., 2014; Magalhães et al., 2016). Its biology remains poorly known; it is oviparous and primarily feeds on arthropods. Because of its small size, it can be preyed upon by birds, mammals, and reptiles (Torres-Carvajal et al., 2006, 2007). In this study, we present the first recorded case of thanatosis in a juvenile of *S. squarrosus*.

On June 21, 2013, during a herpetofauna survey in the municipality of Caldeirão Grande do Piauí, Piauí state, Brazil (7.392°S, 40.408°W), in an area characterized by native vegetation predominantly of *carrasco* and shrubby-arboreal Caatinga, a juvenile specimen of *S. squarrosus* (39 mm snout-vent length and 33 mm tail length) was captured in a pitfall trap with drift fence. The traps were checked in the morning (approximately 19 hours since last inspection). Immediately after collection, the specimen was kept in the shade for three hours, then transported to the field laboratory, where its behavior was observed later that same afternoon. We assume that the specimen did not experience significant stress, such as dehydration or other environmental stressors, prior to the observations. The lizard was placed in a plastic bag with sand and leaf litter from the capture site and was taken to the field lab, where it was placed in a tray (50x30 cm) with sand for photography. During this procedure, the lizard exhibited unusual thanatosis behavior with curious characteristics differing from those reported in other lizards, including display of gestures simulating death.

When the specimen recognized an observer approaching or after a light touch, it quickly ran in the opposite direction for about 10-15 cm and threw itself onto the substrate, flattening its body dorsoventrally against the ground with limbs stretched alternately on each side of the body (Fig. 1B-C), maintaining the same position even when lifted and placed in the observer's palm (Fig. 1D). In some but not all instances, it completely closed its eyes. The lizard was handled ten times and repeated the behav-

ior each time until it seemed to tire and stopped repeating the pattern, remaining merely immobile after short locomotion, without throwing itself onto the ground (which prevented us from recording it). Subsequently, the specimen was euthanized with lidocaine, fixed in 10% formalin, preserved in 70% alcohol, and deposited in the herpetology collection of the Regional University of Cariri, cataloged as URCA-H-5906.

Figura 1. A: A juvenile *Stenocercus squarrosus*, municipality of Caldeirão Grande do Piauí, Piauí, Brazil. B-C: After being lightly touched and moving away from the observer, showing its theatrical performance of thanatosis behavior. D: The lizard maintaining the behavior even while being handled.

Remarkably, the behavior occurred on the ground without direct handling. Although thanatosis manifests in natural environments, most cases are recorded due to fear or stress induced by human manipulation, usually when the individual is being handled (Gerald, 2008; Ribeiro et al. 2010; Gomides & Sousa, 2011; Nunes et al., 2012; Damas-Moreira, 2021). This study reveals unprecedented data on the thanatosis behavior of *Stenocercus squarrosus*. Until now, no defensive behavior had been known for this species. Thanatosis involving running, throwing itself onto the ground, alternating limbs, and remaining in tonic immobility is little known in the genus. Rojas-Suárez et al. (2023) is the only description of a case of thanatosis in *S. erythrogaster* (Hallowell, 1856) in response to direct human handling.

There are some behavioral variations involving thanatosis in lizards, which are related to their responses to external stimuli. This may reflect different types of manipulation observed both in the laboratory and in the natural environment or in the presence of more active predators that feed on constantly moving prey (Machado-Filho et al. 2018; Matias et al. 2024). Furthermore, these physical contact interactions between predator and prey, as well as the duration of immobility, may vary, with longer or shorter periods of interaction (Arduino & Gould, 1984). At least one other case of thanatosis occurred spontaneously due to human proximity in *Podarcis siculus* (Rafinesque-Schmaltz, 1810) (Damas-Moreira, 2021), while the vast majority of thanatosis records have been documented during specimen handling (Carvalho et al. 2011; Travaglia-Cardoso, 2014; Santos et al. 2010; Ribeiro et al. 2010). This includes cases in Tropicoduridae lizards (Galdino & Pereira, 2002; Gomes et al. 2004; Kohlsdorf et al. 2004; Bertoluci et al. 2006; Teles et al. 2018; Costa-Campos & Anaissi, 2020; Rojas-Suárez et al. 2023). In these cases, there do not appear to be significant variations in thanatosis behavioral patterns, which makes the behavior observed in *S. squarrosus* even more noteworthy.

Regarding death-feigning behavior in young lizards, some studies suggest that in certain environments with low temperatures, this behavior may serve as a useful strategy due to the reduction in metabolic activity and the difficulty in thermoregulation, which decreases agility during escape, thereby inducing the animal to remain motionless in the presence of a predator (Miyatake et al.

2008; Montoya-Cruz & Díaz-Flórez, 2023; Travaglia-Cardoso, 2014). However, considering the distribution of *S. squarrosus* in the Caatinga, a semi-arid climate environment, it is less likely that temperature influences this behavior, as the lizard was observed during the day. This suggests that other mechanisms must be involved. Future encounters with this still poorly known species should further our understanding of the biology of the *Stenocercus* group. This study presents a new behavioral discovery that may contribute to a better understanding of the natural history and behavior of lizards.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was carried out under license: 01/2013/Superintendência de Meio Ambiente SMA/Secretaria de Meio Ambiente e Recursos Hídricos do Estado do Piauí– Processo No AA.130.1.003544/13. IJR thanks the “Programa de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico Regional – PDCTR; (Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico - CNPq / Fundação Cearense de Apoio ao Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico FUNCAP – Notice 03/2021, DCT-0182-00049.01.00/21 and 04863348/2022) for the research grant and financial resources (PDCTR 301304/2022-0). SCR thanks the FUNCAP for the research grant and financial resources (BPI-FUNCAP: BP5-0197-00161.01.00/22).

REFERENCES

- Alves, I.G., & Cavalcanti, R. 2024. Death-feigning behaviour in *Colobosaura modesta* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862). *Herpetology Notes* 17: 521-522.
- Arduino P.J., Gould J.L. 1984. Is tonic immobility adaptive? *Animal Behavior* 32:921–923. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-3472\(84\)80173-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-3472(84)80173-6)
- Bauder, J., Macey, J., Stohlgren, K., Day, A., Snow, F., Saffer, A., ... Stevenson, D. Factors influencing the display of multiple defensive behaviors in eastern indigo snakes (*Drymarchon couperi*). 2015. *Herpetological Conservation and Biology* 10(2):559–571.
- Bertoluci, J., Cassimiro, J., Rodrigues, M.T. 2006. Tropicoduridae (Tropicodurid lizards). Death feigning. *Herpetological Review* 37: 472-473.

- Carvalho, R., Lucas, P., Novelli, I. 2011. *Tropidurus Itambere* (Ncn) Tonic Immobility. *Herpetological Review* 42: 279-280.
- Cavalcanti, L.B.Q., Costa, T.B., Colli, G.R., Costa, G.C., França, F.G.R.D. Mesquita, D.O., ... Garda, A.A. 2014. Herpetofauna of protected areas in the Caatinga II: Serra da Capivara National Park, Piauí, Brazil. *Check List* 10:18-27.
- Costa-Campos, C.E., Anaissi, J.S.C. 2020. Death-feigning as defensive behaviour of eight lizard species of the Amazon rainforest. *Herpetological Bulletin* 152: 26-27.
- Damas-Moreira, I. 2021. Playing dead: Lizards show tonic immobility without human handling. *Behaviour* 158: 1-9. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1163/1568539X-bja10089>
- Fuentes, R., Castillo, M., Belton, E., Zambrano, E., Quintero, H., Batista, A. 2021. Dead Snake! A Strategy for Survival: Thanatosis in Some Panamanian Snakes with a Review of Death-feigning in American Snakes. *Reptiles & Amphibians* 28(3): 389-396.
- Galdino, C.A.B., Pereira, E.G. 2002. *Tropidurus nanuzae* (NCN). Death feigning. *Herpetological Review*, 33: 54.
- Gerald, G.W. 2008. Feign versus flight: influences of temperature, body size and locomotor abilities on death feigning in neonate snakes. *Animal Behavior* 75(2): 647-654.
- Gomides, S.C., Sousa, B.M. 2011. *Enyalius perditus*. Death-feigning. *Herpetological Review* 42 (4), 602.
- Gomes, F.R., Kohlsdorf, T., Navas, C.A. 2004. Death-feigning in *Eurolophosaurus divaricatus*: temperature and habituation effects. *Amphibia-Reptilia* 25(3) 321-325.
- Gluesing, E.A. 1983. Collared lizard predation: the effects of conspicuous morphology and movement. *Copeia* 1983: 835-837.
- Hallowell, E. 1856. Notes on reptiles in the collection of the Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia. *Proceedings of the Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia* 8: 221-238.
- Hampreys, R.K., Ruxton, G.D. 2018. A review of thanatosis (death feigning) as an anti-predator behaviour. *Behavioral Ecology and Sociobiology* 72: 22 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00265-017-2436-8>.
- Jelić, D., Vilaj, I. 2011. Remarks on death feigning in *Coronella austriaca* (Laurenti, 1768), *Natrix natrix* (Laurenti, 1768) and *Natrix tessellata* (Laurenti, 1768). *Hyla* 2: 31-33.
- Koslendorf, T., Rodrigues, M.T., Navas, C.A. 2004. *Eurolophosaurus divaricatus* (NCN). Death feigning. *Herpetological Review*, 35: 390.
- Langkilde, T., Schwarzkopf, L., Alford, R. 2003. An ethogram for adult male rainbow skinks, *Carlia jarnoldae*. *Herpetological Journal* 13: 141-148.
- Machado-Filho, P.R., Moya, G.M., Maffei, F. 2018. Death-feigning behaviour in *Iphisa elegans*: the second reported case in the Family Gymnophthalmidae (Reptilia: Squamata). *Acta Amazonica* 48:151-153.
- Magalhaes Jr, A.J.C., Andrade, A.F.A., Moura, G.J.B., Riveiro, L.B., Azevedo Jr. S.M. 2016. New records and ecological niche model of the endemic Caatinga Lizard *Stenocercus squarrosus* Nogueira and Rodrigues, 2006. *Herpetological Review* 47(3): 380-384.
- Matias, C.S.L., Araújo, D.S., Castro, D.P. 2024. Death simulation behavior of the lizard *Lygodactylus klugei* of the Gekkonidae (Reptilia: Squamata) family in northeastern Brazil. *Boletim do Museu Paraense Emílio Goeldi. Ciências Naturais*, 19(1): 928. <http://doi.org/10.46357/bcnaturais.v19i1.928>
- Mesquita, G.S., Ferraz, D., Ramalho, W.P., Machado, I.F., Vaz-Silva, W. 2018. Death-feigning as defensive behavior in blue-tailed microteiid lizard *Micrablepharus atticolus* Rodrigues, 1996. *Herpetology Notes* 11: 1065-1067.
- Miranda, R., Klaczko, J., Tonini, J., Brandao, R. 2022. Escaping from predators: a review of Neotropical lizard's defense traits. *Ethology Ecology and Evolution*. 10.1080/03949370.2022.2082538.
- Miyatake, T. 2001. Diurnal periodicity of death-feigning in *Cylas formicarius* (Coleoptera: Brentidae). *Journal of Insect Behavior* 14: 421-432.
- Miyatake, T., Okada, K., Harano, T. 2008. Negative relationship between ambient temperature and death-feigning intensity in adult *Callosobruchus maculatus* and *Callosobruchus chinensis*. *Physiological Entomology* 33: 83-88. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3032.2007.00607.x>.

- Montoya Cruz, A., Díaz-Flórez, R. 2023. Back from the beyond: Defensive behavior of the Bogota Anadia *Anadia bogotensis* (Squamata: Gymnophthalmidae). *Revista Latinoamericana de Herpetología* 6: 144–147. [10.22201/fc.25942158e.2023.4.814](https://doi.org/10.22201/fc.25942158e.2023.4.814).
- Nogueira, C., Rodrigues, M. 2006. The Genus *Stenocercus* (Squamata: Tropicuridae) in Extra-Amazonian Brazil, With the Description of Two New Species. *South American Journal of Herpetology* 1: 149–165.
- Nunes, J., Elisei, T., Sousa, M.B. 2012. Anti-predator behaviour in the Brazilian lizard *Tropidurus itambere* (Tropicuridae) on a rocky outcrop. *Herpetological Bulletin* 120:22–28.
- Oliver, M.K. 1996. Death-feigning observed in *Hippopsis lemniscata* (Fabricius) (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae). *The Coleopterists' Bulletin* 50: 160–161.
- Resende, A.C., Streatfield, J., Rogers, A. 2025. Thanatosis in juvenile *Notolabrus celidotus*, the New Zealand spotty wrasse. *Acta Ethologica* 28: 45–48. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10211-025-00455-1>.
- Ribeiro, S.C., Roberto, I.J., Sales, D.L., Almeida, W.O. 2009. Distribution extension of *Stenocercus squarrosus* Nogueira and Rodrigues, 2006 (Reptilia, Squamata, Tropicuridae) in Northeastern Brazil. *Biotemas (UFSC)* 22: 165–167.
- Ribeiro, S.C., Souza, J.G.G., Teles, D.A., Almeida, W.O., Guarnieri, M.C. 201. Natural history notes. *Mabuya arajara*. Death-feigning. *Herpetological Review* 41: 494–495.
- Rojas-Suárez, A. E. Montes-Correa, A. Jiménez, J. 2023. Death-feigning in the Red-bellied Ground Lizard, *Stenocercus erythrogaster* (Hallowell 1856) (Squamata: Tropicuridae), in Colombia. *Reptiles & Amphibians* 30: 20083. [10.17161/randa.v30i1.20083](https://doi.org/10.17161/randa.v30i1.20083).
- Rocha, C.F.D. 1993. The set of defense mechanisms in a tropical sand lizard (*Liolaemus lutzae*) of southeastern Brazil. *Ciência e Cultura* 45: 116–122.
- Rocha, C.F.D., Van Sluys, M. 2008. Comportamento de répteis. Pp. 173–188, In Del-Claro, K., Prezoto, F., Sabino, J. (Eds.), *As distintas Faces do Comportamento animal*, editora UniderP, Campo Grande.
- Santos, M.B., Oliveira, M.C.L.M., Verrastro, L., Tozetti, A.M. 2010. Playing dead to stay alive: death-feigning in *Liolaemus occipitalis* (Squamata: Liolaemidae). *Biota Neotropica*, 10(4): 361–364. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1676-06032010000400043>
- Sannolo, M., Gatti, F. Scali, S. 2014. First record of thanatosis behaviour in *Malpolon monspessulanus* (Squamata: Colubridae). *Herpetology Notes* 7: 323.
- Sazima, I. 1974. Experimental predation on the leaf-frog *Phyllomedusa rohdei* by the water snake *Liophis miliaris*. *Journal of Herpetology*. 8(4): 376–377.
- Travaglia-Cardoso, S.R. 2014. Death-feigning in *Tropidurus itambere* (Reptilia: Tropicuridae). *Herpetologia Brasileira* 3: 25–26.
- Teles, D.A., Pinto, C.L.M., Araújo-Filho, J.A., Teixeira, A.A.M. 2018: *Lygodactylus klugei* and *Tropidurus cocorobensis*. Death feigning. *Herpetological Review* 49: 537.
- Torres-Carvajal, O. 2000. Ecuadorian lizards of the genus *Stenocercus* (Squamata: Tropicuridae). *Scientific Papers* 15: 1–38. doi:[10.5962/bhl.title.16286](https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.16286)
- Torres-Carvajal, O., Chulte, J.A. S., Adle, J.E.C. 2006. Phylogenetic relationships of South American lizards of the genus *Stenocercus* (Squamata: Iguania): A new approach using a general mixture model for gene sequence data. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 39:171–185.
- Torres-Carvajal, O., 2007. A taxonomic revision of South American *Stenocercus* (Squamata: Iguania) lizards. *Herpetological Monographs* 21(1): 76–178. <https://doi.org/10.1655/06-001.1>
- Torres-Cervantes, R.J., Hernandez-Ibarra, X., Ramirez-Bautista, A. 2004. *Anelytropsis papillosus* (Mexican blind lizard). Death feigning and autotomy. *Herpetological Review* 35(4): 384.
- Travaglia-Cardoso, S.R. 2014. Death-feigning in *Tropidurus itambere* (Reptilia: Tropicuridae). *Herpetologia Brasileira* 3: 25–26
- Uetz, P., Freed, P., Aguilar, R., Reyes, F., Kudera, J., Hošek, J. (Eds.). 2025. The Reptile Database. Accessible at: <http://www.reptile-database.org>, accessed 25 February 2025.

Vrcibradic, D., Vansluys, M. 2000. *Hyla alvarengai* (NCN). Death feigning and size at maturity. *Herpetological Review* 31: 40-41.

Maria Regilane Belo da Silva “Graduada em Licenciatura Interdisciplinar em Ciências Naturais e Matemática e em Licenciatura em Biologia, ambas pela Universidade Federal do Cariri (UFCA), onde integra o Laboratório de Biologia e Ecologia de Animais Silvestres (LABEAS). Atua como professora da rede pública de ensino, lecionando matemática no Ensino Fundamental na região sul do Ceará.”

“Graduated in Interdisciplinary Licentiate in Natural Sciences and Mathematics and in Licentiate in Biology, both from the Universidade Federal do Cariri (UFCA), where she is a member of the Laboratory of Biology and Ecology of Wild Animals. She works as a public school teacher, teaching Mathematics at the elementary education level in the southern region of Ceará, Brazil.”

João Antonio de Araujo Filho “Bacharel em Ciências Biológicas pela Universidade Regional do Cariri (URCA). Mestre em Bioprospecção Molecular (Biodiversidade) pela Universidade Regional do Cariri (URCA). Doutor em Ciências Biológicas (Zoologia) pela Universidade Federal da Paraíba (UFPB). Pós-doutorado no Programa de Pós- Graduação em Diversidade Biológica e Recursos Naturais da Universidade Regional do Cariri (URCA). Atualmente, é professor de Zoologia da Universidade Regional do Cariri (URCA). Sua pesquisa se concentra na compreensão dos fatores que influenciam a abundância e a ocorrência de endoparasitos associados à herpetologia, particularmente em populações de anfíbios e répteis, bem como as interações entre as espécies e seu ambiente.”

“Bachelor in Biological Sciences from the Regional University of Cariri (URCA). Master’s degree in Molecular Bioprospecting (Biodiversity) from the Regional University of Cariri (URCA). Ph.D. in Biological Sciences (Zoology) from the Federal University of Paraíba (UFPB). Postdoctoral fellowship in the Graduate Program in Biological Diversity and Natural Resources at the Regional University of Cariri (URCA). Currently, Professor of Zoology at the Regional University of Cariri (URCA). His research focuses on understanding the factors that influence the abundance and occurrence of endoparasites associated with herpetology, particularly in amphibian and reptile populations, as well as the interactions between species and their environment.”

Igor Joventino Roberto “Biólogo formado pela Universidade Federal do Ceará (Fortaleza, Ceará, Brasil) e doutor em Zoologia pela Universidade Federal do Amazonas (Manaus, Amazonas, Brasil). Atualmente, Igor é Professor Assistente de Zoologia na Universidade Estadual do Ceará (UECE-FAFIDAM) em Limoeiro do Norte, Ceará, Brasil, e membro do Grupo de Especialistas em Crocodilos da União Internacional para a Conservação da Natureza (IUCN). Sua pesquisa concentra-se em sistemática, taxonomia, história natural e conservação de anfíbios e répteis no nordeste do Brasil. (Foto: Coleman M. Sheehy, III).”

“Is a Biologist who graduated from the Universidade Federal do Ceará (Fortaleza, Ceará, Brazil), and earned his Ph.D. in Zoology from the Universidade Federal do Amazonas (Manaus, Amazonas, Brazil). Currently Igor is an Assistant Professor of Zoology at the Universidade Estadual do Ceará (UECE-FAFIDAM) in Limoeiro do Norte, Ceará, Brazil, and is a member of the Crocodile Specialist Group of the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN). His research is focused on systematics, taxonomy, natural history, and conservation of amphibians and reptiles in northeastern Brazil. (Photographed by Coleman M. Sheehy, III).”

Samuel Cardozo Ribeiro “Professor Adjunto da Universidade Federal do Cariri, Campus Brejo Santo, Ceará. Doutor em Zoologia pela Universidade Federal da Paraíba. Mestre em Biologia Animal pela Universidade Federal de Pernambuco e Bacharel em Ciências Biológicas pela Universidade Regional do Cariri, onde é orientador do Programa de Pós-Graduação em Diversidade Biológica e Recursos Naturais. Membro da Sociedade Brasileira de Herpetologia desde 2009, e membro do Skink Specialist Group da União Internacional para a Conservação da Natureza (IUCN). Desenvolve pesquisas com répteis (Squamata) e anfíbios (Anura), abordando temas como ecologia de populações e comunidades, parasitismo, história natural e sistemática.”

“Adjunct Professor at the Universidade Federal do Cariri, Brejo Santo Campus, Ceará. PhD in Zoology from the Universidade Federal da Paraíba, master’s degree in Animal Biology from the Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, and Bachelor’s in Biological Sciences from the Universidade Regional do Cariri, where he is the advisor for the Postgraduate Program in Biological Diversity and Natural Resources. Member of the Brazilian Society of Herpetology since 2009 and a member of the Skink Specialist Group of the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN). His research focuses on reptiles (Squamata) and amphibians (Anura), addressing topics such as population and community ecology, parasitism, natural history, and systematics.”